

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

METHODS OF MINING CRYPTOCURRENCIES

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Abstract

Obtaining cryptocurrencies is possible in several ways: purchase on specialized trading platforms – cryptocurrency exchanges; direct purchase of digital currency from owners without the participation of intermediaries, as well as purchase in cryptocurrency exchangers and terminals, on sites providing services related to the exchange of cryptocurrencies for fiat currency; purchase of investment products based on crypto assets; as well as mining. Mining is the activity of issuing cryptocurrencies, as well as receiving rewards for validating transactions, accompanied by resource-intensive calculations. There are: standard mining based on the use of special equipment; cloud mining; as well as web mining of cryptocurrencies based on the use of Internet technologies. Each method involves the use of a specific encryption algorithm, which can be in the form of PoW; PoS and PoC. There are various hybrid algorithms: Siacoin (SC); Dash, Decred, Peercoin (PoW+PoS); cryptocurrencies that use a variety of hash functions.

Keywords: digital assets, tokenization, distributed registries, smart contracts, stocks, blockchain, cryptocurrency, mining

The relevance of this work is due to the high importance of studying the cryptocurrency market, which has received its rapid development against the background of a combination of fairly soft monetary policy of key central banks during the coronavirus pandemic, active search for profitability by investors under sanctions restrictions, as well as the needs of individuals and legal entities in instant payments. After all, the purpose of creating cryptocurrencies, as a decentralized type of digital currency, using cryptography as security and control over the creation of new units, is to provide a convenient means of payment, potentially attractive from an investment position. As well as giving cryptocurrencies an anonymous character, allowing them to circumvent regulatory restrictions by eliminating intermediaries, which include banks and payment systems, and transferring the verification function of transactions to a distributed ledger system.

Popularization of financial transactions using cryptocurrencies in order to make the most optimal investment decisions actualizes the analysis of mining methods. The acquisition or receipt of cryptocurrencies is possible in several ways, which A.A. Sitnik structured as follows [1]:

1. The easiest way is to purchase cryptocurrencies on specialized trading platforms – cryptocurrency exchanges. Transactions with cryptocurrencies on exchanges are determined by the following actions:

- by buying cryptocurrencies and receiving them on a crypto wallet;
- by selling cryptocurrencies from different crypto wallets and investor accounts;
- by entering or withdrawing cryptocurrencies from the user's personal wallet to the investor's wallet or account, which was opened by the crypto exchange, in order to carry out trading operations with them;
- exchange of cryptocurrencies for fiat currencies and their withdrawal to the investor's account.

It should be noted that most crypto exchanges attract investors with the opportunity to perform trading operations with the main cryptocurrencies, which can be obtained not only during the purchase process, but also during the mining process. Exchange commissions depend on the type of transactions. If the replenishment of the account on crypto exchanges is made in cryptocurrency, then the commission is usually minimal or not charged at all. For example, in the case of transfers of fiat money to cryptocurrency, a commission is charged not only by the payment system used by the crypto exchange, but also by the crypto exchange itself. In the case of withdrawing cryptocurrencies from a crypto exchange, the situation is similar, however, when withdrawing to a crypto wallet or transferring to another digital currency, the commission is less than when withdrawing to fiat money.

2. Other ways of acquiring cryptocurrencies are represented by the direct purchase of digital currency from owners without the participation of intermediaries, as well as the purchase of cryptocurrencies in cryptocurrency exchangers and terminals, on sites that provide services related to the exchange of cryptocurrencies for fiat currency (including anonymous networks, Darknet). Information about cryptocurrencies purchased by the user is stored on wallets created by the user himself (for example, Bitcoin wallets), as well as on wallets created by a cryptocurrency exchange or a third-party organization.

3. An important trend in recent years is the arrival of institutional investors to the cryptocurrency market, as well as the emergence of financial instruments that are linked to cryptocurrencies. Therefore, one of the ways to obtain cryptocurrency should be called the purchase of investment products based on crypto assets. The bulk of derivatives trading is conducted on cryptocurrency platforms, however, there is a tendency to launch cryptocurrency derivatives on traditional exchanges as well.

4. Mining, which is an activity that can result in the issuance of cryptocurrencies, as well as receiving cryptocurrencies as a reward for validating transactions, accompanied by resource-intensive calculations..

Before considering the methods, let's reveal the essence of the concept of "mining", which has several approaches that coincide in most cases. Therefore, let us turn to the opinion of L.I. Sergeev, D.L. Sergeev and A.L. Yudanova, which most fully reveals the concept [2]. The authors consider mining as a process of "mining" cryptocurrency, the issue of which is not regulated by anyone. It is clarified that the process works thanks to blockchain technology - a chain of blocks, each of which stores information about a separate transaction. At the same time, the efficiency of the blockchain is directly dependent on the computing power of computers connected to the chain.

M.A. Chistyakov points out that mining is characterized as the process of a person using equipment belonging to him in order to perform calculations necessary for the functioning of distributed registry systems of a certain crypto asset. Clarifies that attracting users to carry out mining is not an obligatory property of cryptocurrencies, since maintaining a distributed ledger system is also possible by a predetermined circle of people [3].

It is also necessary to determine the essence of cryptocurrency mining, which, for example, A.V. Yennik defines in the fact that a large number of computers that are not connected to each other, through a special program (miner) provide solutions to mathematical computational problems necessary for the functioning of the blockchain. As a result, a cryptocurrency is created, which miners receive as a reward for their work by crediting to a special wallet address (account). The account address can be a "cold" one stored on a computer, as well as a "hot" one or a crypto exchange wallet [4].

Practice has developed several methods of mining cryptocurrencies:

- standard mining of cryptocurrencies based on the use of special equipment;
- cloud mining of cryptocurrencies;
- as well as web mining of cryptocurrencies based on the use of Internet technologies.

1. Standard mining dates back to 2009, when novice miners carried out the "mining" of cryptocurrencies on ordinary desktop computers and laptops. Later, simple PCs stopped coping with calculations and multi-core powerful graphics cards were required for further work. An important tool for mining has also become a power supply capable of withstanding the load. Today, standard mining is carried out through the use of various equipment, not including classic video cards:

- through the processor;
- using multiple GPUs at once;
- using special equipment designed to mine certain digital coins.

2. Cloud mining is a variant of "mining" cryptocurrency, which appeared after the onset of difficulties with the purchase of powerful computing equipment. In cloud mining, the user rents equipment over the Internet from a company that provides such services. Each side has its own benefit. Miners accelerate the production of cryptocurrencies and make a profit, companies that lease equipment receive a commission and rent. The main advantage of the work is the absence of the need for the miner to monitor the state of computer technology. All transactions are confirmed in chronological order, the resulting distortion entails the cancellation of the entire block by the program.

Practice has developed different ways of cloud mining cryptocurrencies [5]:

- paid, based on rent and commission by the company;
- free (Bitcoin faucets) that you can use.

There are also three forms of cloud mining of cryptocurrencies:

- hosting, in which all the capacities that are leased are from the service provider;
- virtual hosting, in which the user rents the entire server and installs their own software;
- power rental, in which the user does not have access to the system software.

3. Web mining, which is one of the least popular ways to "mine" cryptocurrency. It is carried out through sites where you need to register and install a special program. Website owners use the power of all users who register on their resource to mine cryptocurrencies. To assess the possibility of carrying out web mining, an analysis of the size of possible investments is carried out, a comparison with profit, as well as taking into account external factors that complicate the "extraction" of cryptocurrencies. Special websites - "cryptocurrency calculators" - help with these calculations [6].

Separately, popular encryption algorithms for mining should be named.

The PoW algorithm. The encryption algorithm sets the parameters for creating cryptoblocks, but it cannot fully guarantee the integrity of the network. Miners and coin owners are members of the network and can make changes to the blockchain by generating new blocks and making transactions. Special consensus-

building algorithms are used to control changes in the ecosystem structure. Most networks use Proof-of-Work and Proof-of-Stake. Allows the owner of the highest computing power to find more blocks and receive more rewards. A significant increase in productivity ensures the capture of more than 50% of the network's capacity and its actual management, undermining the principle of decentralization. The most common ones are: Bitcoin, Miner, Z Cash, etc. The PoW algorithm was the main one during the formation of the cryptocurrency market, but today it is being replaced by other, more energy-efficient algorithms.

The content of the network nodes that perform calculations, serve as routers, validators, and perform various other functions. This algorithm is called PoS (betting) from the English proof of betting. Implies the existence of a second layer of the network, which ensures its functioning. This is usually done by computers running software that performs node functions – the so-called nodes or masternodes. Their owners receive remuneration for their constant work to maintain the network's operability. To become the owner of a node, it is necessary to have a certain amount of cryptocurrencies of this platform, which are pledged. Profit does not depend on the power of the mining farm, which is not needed for the PoS algorithm at all, but on the amount of cryptocurrency in the wallet. The only condition is the constant synchronization of the crypto vault with the network. The longer the shelf life of assets, the higher the dividends. The most famous cryptocurrencies of the algorithm are Sibcoin, Horizon, Nem, BlackCoin, etc.

Information storage. This algorithm is called PoC (proof of capacity). They receive a reward for renting

out space on their disk. The most famous cryptocurrencies of this algorithm are Burst, Storj.

Sharing an existing communication channel and network access. This algorithm makes it possible to earn money by sharing a WiFi access point, by selling unused SMS packages to the corporate sector, as well as other ways to benefit from renting out existing communication capabilities. An example of such a cryptocurrency is the QLC Chain project.

In addition, there are various hybrid mining algorithms, for example [7]:

- Siacoin (SC), which is mined using the PoW (Blake2b hashing) and PoC algorithms;
- Dash, Decred, Peercoin (PoW+PoS);
- cryptocurrencies using a variety of hash functions (for example, Digibyte with five PoW algorithms: Groestl, Skein, Qubit, Scrypt and Sha256).

Существуют и другие, более новые алгоритмы для майнинга, которые в основном являются доработанными копиями уже давно существующих алгоритмов, но иногда являются оригинальными разработками, например, PHI1612 – гибридный пр+Пос энергоэффективный алгоритм, оптимизированный для видеокарт и процессоров, имеющий защиту от поим и с NiceHash, применяемый в таких криптовалютах, как: LUXCoin (люкс); Folm монета (FOLM). Он использует комбинацию из трех алгоритмизаторов: Skein, JH, Cubehash, Fungue, Ghost и Echo.

The most popular cryptocurrencies with encryption algorithms are shown in Table 3.

Table 3

Popular cryptocurrencies with encryption algorithms

№	The name of the cryptocurrency	Date of creation	Stock designation	The encryption algorithm	The consensus algorithm
1	Bitcoin	2008	BTC	SHA256	PoW
2	Ethereum	2015	ETH	Ethash	PoW
3	Ripple	2013	XRP	ECDSA	-
4	Bitcoin Cash	2017	BCH	SHA256	PoW
5	EOS	2018	EOS	SHA-256+ ECDSA	PoS
6	Stellar Lumen	2015	Lumen (XLM)	Ed25519	Stellar Consensus Protocol
7	Litecoin	2011	LTC	Scrypt	PoW
8	Cardano	2017	ADA	Ed25519	PoS
9	Monero	2014	XMR	RandomX	PoW
10	Dash	2014	DASH	X11	PoS+PoW
11	NEO (изначально AntShares)	2014	NEO	SHA-256+ RIPEMD160	PoW
12	Ethereum-Classic	2015	ETC	ETCHash	PoW
13	NEM	2015	XEM	Catapult	Proof-of-Importance
14	Dogecoin	2013	DOGE	Scrypt	PoW
15	ZCash	2016	ZEC	Equihash	PoW
16	BitcoinGold	2017	BTG	Zhash	PoW
17	Lisk	2016	LSK	Ed25519	PoS
18	Bytecoin	2012	BCN	CryptoNight	PoW
19	Nextcoin	2013	NXT	Ed25519	PoS
20	Decred	2015	DCR	Blake256	PoW+PoS
21	DigiByte	2014	DGB	Groestl, Skein, Qubit, Scrypt и Sha256	PoW

22	ICON	2017	ICX (токены ERC20)	LFT	Расш. PoS
23	Steem	2016	STEEM	SHA256	PoS+PoW
24	Expanse	2015	EXP	Ethash	PoW
25	Stratis	2016	STRAT	X13	PoS
26	Ubiq	2017	UBQ	Ubqhash	PoW
27	Monacoin	2014	MONA	Lyra2REv2	PoW
28	Vertcoin	2014	VTC	Lyra2REv2	PoW
29	Peercoin	2012	PPC	SHA256	PoW+PoS
30	Siacoin	2015	SC	Blake2B-Sia	PoW+PoStorage
31	Burst	2014	BURST	Shabal256	PoC
32	Ravencoin	2018	RVN	KawPow	PoW
33	Grin	2019	GRIN	Cuckatoo32 Cuckarooz29	PoW
34	Beam	2019	BEAM	BeamHash 3	PoW
35	Conflux	2020	CFX	Octopus	PoW
36	Veil	2019	VEIL	RandomX ProgPoW	PoW

Source: compiled by the author according to the official website of the portal "ALTCOIN.LOG" / What Is Cryptocurrency Mining 2023: Why Is It Needed. - URL: <https://altcoinlog.com/chto-takoe-maining-cryptocurrency/> (date of application: 15.09.2023 r). – Text: electronic

The reasons for investing in cryptocurrencies are quite diverse: owning cryptocurrency as part of a long-term investment strategy; distrust of the traditional financial system; the possibility of quick profits from short-term trading transactions; fear of missing out, etc. However, the main motivating factor in making investments in cryptocurrency is the expectation of high profitability.

Thus, it can be concluded that obtaining cryptocurrencies is possible in several ways: purchase on specialized trading platforms – cryptocurrency exchanges; direct purchase of digital currency from owners without the participation of intermediaries, as well as purchase in cryptocurrency exchangers and terminals, on sites providing services related to the exchange of cryptocurrencies for fiat currency; purchase of investment products based on on crypto assets; as well as mining. Mining is the activity of issuing cryptocurrencies, as well as receiving rewards for validating transactions, accompanied by resource-intensive calculations. There are: standard mining based on the use of special equipment; cloud mining; as well as web mining of cryptocurrencies based on the use of Internet technologies. Each method involves the use of a specific encryption algorithm, which can be in the form of PoW; PoS and PoC. There are various hybrid algorithms: Siacoin (SC); Dash, Decred, Peercoin (PoW+PoS); cryptocurrencies that use a variety of hash functions.

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